

RECYCLING OF WOVEN CARBON FIBER PATCHES FROM LAMINATED CFRP BY MEANS OF INDUCTION HEATING

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a potentially resource-efficient new fiber-matrix separation process for end-of-life (EOL) – carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) is presented. This process makes it possible to extract well-defined patches of the carbon fiber (CF) fabric out of laminated EOL components. The underlying concept is to selectively heat the CF by induction heating to affect the fiber matrix interface and hereby enable the fiber-matrix separation. Contrary to most common recycling processes there is no need to break the majority of molecular bonds by thermal energy to convert the matrix into the gas phase. The energy transfer is realized by an induction-based warming of the electroconductive fibers by dissipative heating mechanisms.

In the present study, a laminated CFRP plate was separated into single CF plies preserving the textile structure of the fabric. A Scanning-Electron-Microscopy (SEM) analysis of the extracted plies reveals no degradation effects of the fiber surfaces. The chemical composition of the CF surfaces is examined by X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). Single fiber tensile tests show negligible degradation of the tensile strength and the modulus of the recycled carbon fibers (rCF) compared to virgin carbon fibers (vCF).

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to its high strength, high modulus and low density, there is an increasing demand for CFRP as a structural material in lightweight applications in the fields of transport (e.g. automotive, aerospace), energy (e.g. wind energy) and consumer goods (e.g. sports equipment). Today, the worldwide demand of vCF is estimated to be 70.000 - 100.000 t/a, with an annual growth rate expected to be 17 %, according to different scenarios [1]. As the production of carbon fibers is highly energy- and resource-consuming efficient recycling processes of carbon fiber reinforced polymers are of major interest with regard to economic and ecological factors [2]. Furthermore, recycling rates are increasingly regulated by legal requirements such as the EU directive for end-of-life vehicles (200/53/EC) [3, 4].

As a result many recycling processes for CFRP have been developed and improved. Well established are mechanical recycling, like grinding and milling, thermal recycling, like the fluidised-bed process and pyrolysis as well as chemical recycling, which includes solvolysis and supercritical fluids. Typically, the recycling products of these processes are disordered short fibers resulting in a decrease of mechanical properties of second generation CFRPs [5-8]. Typical treatment times of these processes are of the order of hours.

In this study a new approach for the separation of fiber and matrix, based on a selective induction heating of the CF in a laminated CFRP, is presented. During this process, CF patches are extracted preserving the original textile structure of the fabric plies. The further processing of these rCF patches may lead to improved mechanical properties of second generation CFRP compared to short fiber reinforcements. The induction heating process facilitates fast process times. In the present study, a parametric study on typical process parameters like the coupling distance (distance between induction coil and the CFRP sample) and the set temperatures is presented. The morphology of the extracted plies is characterized by Scanning-Electron-Microscopy, the chemical composition of the CF surfaces is

examined by X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy. For an investigation of the mechanical properties of the rCF single fiber tensile tests are performed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The induction heating of CF in a CFRP is a direct heating method which appears to have advantages compared to heating mechanisms like convection, heat radiation or thermal conduction, since it has the potential to realize a separation process which is less energy- and time-consuming.

The heating process in CFRP-materials is realised by current loops formed by the fabric plies which enables the formation of eddy currents based on an applied alternating magnetic field [9].

In the literature three possible heating mechanisms of carbon fibers in CFRPS are discussed: Joule losses within the fibers, contact resistance at fiber intersections and the dielectric hysteresis of the matrix material. [9-13]

Fig. 1 shows a schematic illustration of the experimental setup for the fiber-matrix separation by inductive heating.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the experimental setup for the induction heating process.

The generation of the magnetic field is achieved by an induction coil which is fed by a high frequency (HF) electric generator TruHeat HF 5005 (Trumpf). It controls the applied voltage, its frequency, and power. The induction coil is a quadratic flat coil with an edge length of about 60 mm (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Induction coil geometry.

The required power of the HF generator to achieve the desired set temperature is controlled via pyrometer measurement of the surface temperature.

A constant nitrogen flow in the sample chamber prevents oxidation of the carbon fibers and ensures a controlled removal of the exhaust gases. A thermal imaging (IR) camera is used to monitor the temperature distribution on the sample surface. For a static position of the sample relative to the induction coil an inhomogeneous heating pattern is observed (see Fig. 3).

For all experiments a motion pattern, consisting of nine positions of the CFRP sample relative to the induction coil, is necessary to enable a sufficiently homogeneous heating of the sample. Each step of the pattern means a heating time of 30s at the selected set temperature. An overall heating time of 4.5 min for each sample is sufficient to separate fiber and matrix.

Figure 3: Thermal image of an inductive heated CFRP sample after a heating time of 30s, a coupling distance of 16.56 mm and a set temperature of 200°C.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Material and sample preparation

The specimen investigated in the present study are laminated CFRP plates consisting of twelve plain weave fabric layers of Hexcel 48192 C 1270 ST [14] carbon fibers infiltrated with a Hexcel HexFlow RTM6 [15] matrix system via the vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) process. The samples were sawn into the desired geometry (in this case: 60 mm x 60 mm) for the separation process.

3.2 Scanning-Electron-Microscopy (SEM)

The surfaces of the separated fiber patches are investigated by means of Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (DSM 982 Gemini, Zeiss). Therefore, the fibers are fixed on a specimen holder by

a carbon tape and sputtered with a thin layer of gold. The acceleration voltage is 1 kV.

3.3 X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

The CF samples are fixed onto a sample specimen by a gold frame for the shielding of unwanted measuring signals. The XPS analysis is conducted using a monochromatic X-Ray tube under a take-off angle of 65° . An aluminum cathode is used for recording the XPS spectra. At first a survey spectrum (binding energy 1386.7 eV – 0 eV) was taken for each sample. The applied pass energy was 50 eV and a step width of 0.5 eV. The survey spectra was followed by high resolution scanning over C1s range (300 eV – 280 eV) with a pass energy of 17 eV and a step width of 0.05 eV. Charging effects are avoided by grounding the electroconductive CF samples.

The survey spectrum gives the carbon-, oxygen- and nitrogen-concentration on the CF surface. The line shape used is a Gaussian-Lorentzian product function with a Shirley type background.

3.4 Single fiber tensile tests

Single fiber tensile tests on separated CF and vCF were performed to determine tensile strength and modulus.

The single fiber tensile tests are performed according to the norm ASTM D 3379 – 75 on a Favimat+ (Textechno). Traverse speed during test is 0.5 mm/min. The clamping length is set to 25 mm. For each type of sample 20 tensile tests are conducted.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An extraction of the individual carbon fabric plies out of the CFRP plate was successful for all coupling distances and set temperatures used. In Fig. 4, a photograph of twelve CF plies extracted from one CFRP plate is shown. The textile structure is preserved during a subsequent mechanical handling of the carbon fiber patches.

First examinations show that some residual material is left on the fiber surface for the more gentle treatment conditions. The loss of matrix material is determined by a weighing procedure before and after the separation process. The loss of matrix material for each sample can be calculated individually from the fiber volume ratio and the densities of fiber and matrix material.

Figure 4: Photograph of twelve CF plies, extracted from a 60 x 60 mm CFRP component by the induction heating process.

4.1 Influence of set temperature and coupling distance on mass loss during the induction heating process

To investigate the influence of different parameters of the induction heating process the same type

of samples is treated with different set temperatures and at different coupling distances.

Four different set temperatures as measured on the sample surface were selected. Reference point for the temperature measurement was the hottest zone which is pointed out exemplarily in Fig. 3. The set temperature ranges from 240°C over 260°C and 280°C up to 320°C. The coupling distance was varied from 16.56 mm to 20.40 mm and finally 27.06 mm.

The influence of the set temperature and the coupling distance at two set temperatures is shown in Fig. 5. The mass loss of matrix material during the separation process is used as an indicator for the effect of the induction heating of the CFRP plate.

Figure 5: Investigation of the mass loss of matrix material during induction treatment (a) Variation of set temperature (b) Variation of coupling distance at a temperature of 240°C and 280°C

All samples examined can be separated into twelve single plies though the loss of matrix material is quite different at different set temperatures (see Fig. 5 (a)). As expected, a treatment of the CFRP plates with higher set temperatures causes a higher loss of matrix material.

Fig. 5 (b) shows the dependency of matrix material loss on coupling distance. It can be seen that higher distances between coil and sample cause a lower loss of matrix material. A possible explanation of this effect could be that although the set temperature remains constant the average temperature of the sample decreases with increasing coupling distance due to a decrease of the magnetic field intensity with growing coupling distance. As a consequence, the induced current density decreases with the distance of coil and sample. [16]

4.2 SEM analysis

The surface of the separated carbon fibers are investigated by SEM analysis. In Fig. 6 a representative selection of SEM micrographs of the four different separated CF surfaces is shown.

Figure 6: SEM analysis of the fiber surfaces after the separation process (a) set temperature 240°C (b) set temperature 260°C (c) set temperature 280°C (d) set temperature 320°C.

It can be seen that most parts of the fiber surfaces are free from residues like char or resin material. In agreement with the increasing mass loss with increasing set temperature (Fig. 5 (a)), the amount of remaining matrix material on the fiber surfaces decreases from Fig. 6 (a) to Fig. 6 (d). No degradation of the fiber surfaces can be detected for the samples investigated.

4.3 Chemical surface analysis of the recycled carbon fibers by XPS measurements

Furthermore an investigation of the surface composition by XPS is performed. A thermally desized vCF is examined as a reference. Treatment conditions for the thermal desizing are 800°C for one hour under a constant nitrogen flow. In Fig. 7 the elemental analysis is shown to compare and evaluate the influence of the different separation parameters on the surface composition.

Figure 7: XPS elemental analysis of the rCF surfaces in comparison with a thermally desized vCF.

Carbon, oxygen and nitrogen can be detected on all fiber surfaces. It can be assumed that the nitrogen content on the thermally desized vCF originates from the polyacrylonitrile precursor. A lower amount of carbon and a higher amount of oxygen and nitrogen on the fiber surface compared to the thermally desized vCF is characteristic for the examined separated fibers. There is no significant change of the O/C-ratio with increasing set temperature and only a slight increase of the N/C-ratio (see Table 1).

	O/C	N/C	(N+O)/C
th. desized vCF	0,042	0,005	0,047
rCF (240°C)	0,073	0,015	0,088
rCF (260°C)	0,064	0,055	0,119
rCF (280°C)	0,053	0,060	0,114
rCF (320°C)	0,060	0,060	0,121

Table 1: Surface composition of vCF compared to the different rCF by means of a comparison of the distinct elemental ratios.

Therefore, it can be concluded that set temperatures between 240°C and 260°C are sufficient temperatures to separate carbon fiber fabric plies out of a CFRP plate.

4.4 Single-fiber tensile tests

The analysis of the separated rCFs mechanical properties is necessary to determine if there exists a loss of properties due to the separation process. In Fig. 8 the tensile modulus (a) and the tensile strength (b) of all separated fibers compared to the vCF are depicted.

Figure 8: Single fiber tensile test (a) tensile modulus (b) tensile strength.

The reduction of the tensile modulus of the separated fibers compared to the vCF is less 5% (see Fig. 8 (a)). The only exception appears to be rCF (240°C). This can be explained by the fact that the apparent diameter of the fiber is increased due to residues of resin on the fiber. The diameter is automatically taken into account in the single fiber tensile test which therefore results in apparent reduction of tensile strength and modulus. This is indicated by the greyed out bars in Fig. 8. If the same fiber diameter is assumed for rCF (240°C) the tensile strength and modulus agree with that of the vCF.

In Fig. 8 (b) the tensile strength of the separated fibers compared to the vCF are displayed. It should be noted that large standard deviations are common for single fiber tensile testing due to the sensitivity of the single fibers to defects. The tensile strength of vCF, rCF (240°C) and rCF (260°C) are the same in the margins of error. The samples rCF (280°C) and rCF (320°C) show a reduction of up to 30%. Although this is still within the margin of error we believe that this degradation is real. This may indicate that the temperature of the fibers is well above the set temperature in this process.

In summary the tensile modulus of the rCF is unaffected by the separation process for all the set temperatures investigated, whereas the tensile strength is unaffected up to rCF (260°C).

5 CONCLUSION

The presented study has shown that the designed experimental setup enables the separation of a laminated CFRP plate into its single plies while preserving the structure of the fabric under defined conditions. The selective heating of the CF by induction heating affects the fiber matrix interface and allows for the separation of the single fabric plies. Suitable parameters for the inductive assisted separation of the fiber plies were determined with regard to the realization of a resource-efficient recycling process. The conservation of the textile structure enables a recycling product with improved mechanical properties compared to short fiber products. In addition, the selectivity and the short time duration of the heating process promises energy savings compared to established fiber-matrix separation processes.

Based on the shown findings, we conclude that the presented method has great potential to contribute to an economic, high quality recycling process.

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